

Use of zinc oxide particulate system as a photocatalyst : photobleaching of Rose Bengal

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Manuscript received 5 October 2001, revised 16 June 2002, accepted 22 August 2002

Photocatalytic bleaching of Rose Bengal (RB) on zinc oxide powder was carried out in presence of light. The effects of variation of different parameters, like concentration of RB, pH, amount and particle size of the semiconductor and light intensity on the rate of bleaching were observed. A tentative mechanism for the photocatalytic bleaching of RB has been proposed.

Chen and Chou¹ reported photobleaching of methyl orange in aqueous solution with suspended titanium dioxide. Photocatalytic degradation of cetylpyridinium chloride over TiO₂ has been reported by Singhal *et al.*². Similar photocatalytic reactions of xylidine ponceau and orange-G dyes by ZnO powder has been reported by Sharma *et al.*³. Xie *et al.*⁴ observed photoassisted degradation of dyes in the presence of Fe^{III} and H₂O₂ under visible light. Photocatalytic mineralization of methylene blue using buoyant TiO₂ coated polystyrene beads has been studied by Fabiyi and Shelton⁵. Photo-oxidation of alizarin red in TiO₂ dispersions under visible illumination was carried out by Liu *et al.*⁶. Kim and Yoom⁷ prepared a new photocatalyst for photoreduction of methyl orange in aqueous medium by encapsulating TiO₂/Y-zeolite. Photocatalytic degradation of brilliant green and crystal violet over zinc oxide has been investigated by Ameta *et al.*⁸. Ramazol red was degraded in presence of ZnO photocatalyst by Sivakumar *et al.*⁹. Neppolian *et al.*¹⁰ reported photodegradation of some textile dyes over ZnO. Similarly, ZnO was used in the slurry and thin film form for photocatalytic degradation of acid green-16¹⁷. Photocatalytic reduction of methyl yellow on CdS nanoparticles mediated in reverse micelles was observed by Zang and Shen¹². Nasr *et al.*¹³ reported photocatalytic reduction of azo dyes like naphthol blue black and disperse blue-79. Vinodgopal *et al.*¹⁴ used coupled SnO₂/TiO₂ system for photocatalytic degradation of a textile azo dye. No work has yet been reported on photocatalytic bleaching of rose bengal (a fluorescein dye) although it is extensively used in dyeing and printing industries. This was the motivation behind the present work.

Results and Discussion

The photocatalytic bleaching of RB was observed at λ_{\max} 559 nm. The results for a typical run are given in Table I.

Table I

[RB] = 1.0×10^{-5} M, pH = 7.3, temp. = 308 K, light intensity = 26.0 mW cm⁻², zinc oxide = 0.50 g

Time (min)	Optical density
0.0	0.627
15.0	0.445
30.0	0.306
45.0	0.213
60.0	0.147
75.0	0.102
90.0	0.070
105.0	0.049
120.0	0.034
135.0	0.024
150.0	0.017
165.0	0.012
170.0	0.010

The optical density of RB solution was found to decrease with the increase in the time of irradiation, thus indicating that RB was consumed on irradiation.

Effect of pH variation : The effect of pH on the rate of bleaching of RB was investigated in the pH range 6.0–10.0. The dye solution was bleached and semiconductor zinc oxide dissolved in highly acidic media and, therefore, photocatalytic bleaching could not be investigated in lower pH range.

Table 2. Effect of variation of pH[RB] = 1.0×10^{-5} M, zinc oxide = 0.50 g, temp = 308 K, light intensity = 26.0 mW cm⁻²

pH	$10^4 k$ (s ⁻¹)
6.0	1.4
6.5	2.5
7.0	3.4
7.5	4.4
8.0	5.6
8.5	6.5
9.0	7.4
9.5	8.5
10.0	9.5

The rate of the bleaching of RB was found to increase with increase in pH of the medium. This observation is similar to that reported earlier¹⁵. In alkaline medium, there is a greater probability for the formation of hydroxyl radicals (OH[•]), which can act as an oxidant, thus, increasing the rate of photocatalytic bleaching of the dye.

Effect of RB concentration : Effect of variation of dye concentration was also studied and the results are given in Table 3.

Table 3. Effect of Rose Bengal concentrationpH = 7.3, zinc oxide = 0.50 g, temp. = 308 K, light intensity = 26.0 mW cm⁻²

[RB] 10 ⁵ M	$10^4 k$ (s ⁻¹)
0.10	9.9
0.25	8.1
0.50	6.2
0.75	4.9
1.00	4.0
1.25	3.2
1.50	2.5
1.75	2.1
2.00	1.8

It is evident from the data that with the increasing [RB], reaction rate decreases. It can be explained on the basis that as the concentration of RB is increased, it may start acting like a filter for the incident light. Hence, on increasing the concentration of dye, only a fraction of the light intensity will reach the semiconductor surface. This decrease in intensity will in turn retard the reaction rate.

Effect of zinc oxide : The results of effect of amount of semiconductor zinc oxide powder on the rate of bleaching reveal that the value of k increases with increase in the

amount of zinc oxide but the time taken for bleaching of RB solution decreases with the increase in the amount of semiconductor zinc oxide. This increase in the rate of bleaching may be attributed to increase in the exposed surface area of the semiconductor. But after a certain limit (0.70 g), if the amount of zinc oxide is increased further, there will be no increase in the exposed surface area of the photocatalyst and hence no additional effect on the rate of photocatalytic bleaching of RB.

Effect of variation of light intensity : The effect of intensity of light on the photocatalytic bleaching of RB was observed and the results are reported in Table 4.

Table 4. Effect of light intensitypH = 7.3, zinc oxide = 0.50 g, temp. = 308 K, [RB] = 1.0×10^{-5} M

Intensity of light mW cm ⁻²	$10^4 k$ (s ⁻¹)
11.0	1.4
15.0	2.1
18.0	2.6
26.0	4.0
40.0	4.7
60.0	5.8

The results indicate that bleaching action is accelerated as the intensity of light is increased. Further increase in the intensity of light will increase the temperature of the dye solution, thus thermal reactions may occur in place of photocatalytic reactions.

Effect of particle size of zinc oxide : The effect of particle size of zinc oxide on the rate of bleaching of RB was also investigated. The results reveal that as the particle size of the semiconductor (0.80 μg) is increased (upto 4.00 μm), there is a corresponding decrease in the reaction rate. This may be due to the fact that on increasing the particle size (keeping the amount constant) of the photocatalyst, the overall surface area of the semiconductor will decrease, thus resulting into a decrease in the rate of bleaching of RB.

Mechanism :

On the basis of the observed data, the following tentative mechanism has been proposed for photocatalytic bleaching of RB. The semiconductor (SC) will be excited on exposure to give SC^{*}. This excited state will provide an electron (e⁻) in the conduction band and a hole in the valence band. The latter will generate hydroxyl radical (OH[•]) from hydroxyl ions, which will oxidize the dye to its leuco form,

The participation of OH^\bullet as an active oxidizing species was confirmed by carrying out same reaction in presence of some hydroxyl radical scavengers like isopropanol, where rate of bleaching was drastically reduced.

Experimental

Rose Bengal (HM) and zinc oxide (Merck) were used. The photocatalytic bleaching of RB was studied in the presence of semiconducting zinc oxide. A $1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ RB solution in double-distilled water was used as a stock solution. The dye solution ($1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$; 200.0 ml) in presence of zinc oxide semiconductor (0.50 g) was irradiated under light (intensity 26.0 mW cm^{-2}) using a 200 W tungsten lamp (Sylvania Laxman) with magnetic stirring. Sunlight was used for higher intensities of light. The intensity of light was measured by a Suryamapi (CEL-SM 201) instrument. A water filter was used to cut off thermal radiations. The pH was measured by a Systronics 324 pH meter. The desired pH of the solution was adjusted by the addition of previously standardized sulfuric acid and sodium hydroxide solutions. The solution was made free from semiconductor particles by filtering through a G-3 sintered glass crucible. A Systronics 108 spectrophotometer was used for measuring optical density at different time intervals, whereas λ_{max} of the dye was determined with a Shimadzu UV 240 spectrophotometer.

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